

The high strain rate deformation of a high-strength, high-toughness 10Ni-0.1C steel

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Abstract

We have characterized the propensity for adiabatic shear band formation under dynamic deformation conditions in an ultra-high strength (1.1GPa) 10Ni steel and demonstrated that in spite of its outstanding static toughness, this steel is highly prone to shear localization and failure. Specifically, microstructural evolution during deformation of a Fe-10 Ni-0.1C-Cr,Mo,V steel was examined. In the high-strength condition (influenced by tempering parameters), the steel has a lath martensite microstructure with a mean lath size of ~60 nm, and MC carbides dispersed in it with a mean size of ~20 nm. During compressive dynamic deformation using a split Hopkinson bar (strain rates of 1000 to 4000 per second), depending on strain and strain rate, shear localization occurs and is accompanied by an optically visible shear band (~20 micrometers wide). In the situation where the localization process is in its early stages (lower rates, lower global height strains, or both), the microstructure shows severe local deformation within the band but the initial microstructure is still discernible.